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Research article

**DISTRIBUTION OF DIFFERENT SLEEP BEHAVIOURS
AMONG THE MEDICAL STUDENTS IN ALLAMA IQBAL
MEDICAL COLLEGE LAHORE**Maria Batool¹, Aisha Akbar², Hira Javaid³¹Jinnah Hospital, Lahore, ²Karachi Medical & Dental College, Karachi, ³Mayo Hospital, Lahore.**Article Received:** July 2019**Accepted:** August 2019**Published:** September 2019**Abstract:**

According to the recent statistics, around 32.6% of the patients report in different hospitals and healthcare facilities with the complaint of sleep disturbance and its associated symptoms.

***Material and Methods:** This study was conducted in Allama Iqbal Medical College Lahore. A total of 86 male and female students from different classes was included in this study. A predefined questionnaire was served. The data was collected and analyzed using SPSS Ver. 23.0.*

***Results:** There were 42 male (48.83%) and 44 female (51.16%) students. The mean age of the students was 22.78±2.24 years. Regarding the sleep patterns, 67 students (77.90%) responded that they don't get enough sleep during their academic year. Thirty five students (40.69%) told they get proper sleep despite their hectic routines.*

***Conclusion:** Most of the medical students have irregular sleep patterns and they don't sleep well. It is associated with their academic assignments, examinations, irregular hospital routines, electricity issues and tiredness after the commute.*

Keywords: *Medical education, sleep, emotional intelligence.*

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INTRODUCTION:

According to the literature, one third of the young individuals are suffering from different kinds of sleep disturbances worldwide and that the number is increasing day by day. The reasons of these sleep disturbances are different and dependent on different factors. According to the recent statistics, around 32.6% of the patients report in different hospitals and healthcare facilities with the complaint of sleep disturbance and its associated symptoms [1-3]. Individuals who suffer from insomnia for a longer period of time usually develop complications such as musculoskeletal disorders, anger, hypertension, mental health, irritability and cerebrovascular symptoms [4,5].

A lot of medical students have to go through different pressures throughout their academic career. Different assignments, ward-rotations, practical classes, and hospital duties make them tired early. The situation is aggravated if they don't get enough time for sleep hence leading to a disturbed life balance, poor quality of life. According to some studies, medical students have a poor sleep quality that is way different from health standards and that experienced by modern society [6].

The sleep quality impacts a lot on the life of a medical student. In this case, they might not concentrate on their studies and assignments, might not attend their ward rotations properly and might not perform their hospital duties in an efficient way. This will ultimately impact their professional growth, decision power, and emotional intelligence.

The purpose of this study to determine the distribution of different sleep behaviors among medical students. This study will help us in finding the root causes of disturbed sleep among them and will enable us to

formulate certain guidelines in order to ensure proper and quality sleep among them.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This study was conducted in Allama Iqbal Medical College Lahore. A total of 86 male and female students from different classes was included in this study. The purpose of the study was explained to them and consent was taken. Confidentiality of each student was ensured. A predefined questionnaire was served. The data was collected and analyzed using SPSS Ver. 23.0. The categorical variables such as gender, class were presented as frequencies and percentages, quantitative variables such as age were however presented as mean and standard deviation.

RESULTS:

There were 42 male (48.83%) and 44 female (51.16%) students. The mean age of the students was 22.78 ± 2.24 years. The mean age of the male and female students was 23.27 ± 2.14 years and 21.87 ± 2.53 years respectively. The minimum age noticed was 21 years and maximum age noticed was 26 years. Twenty-five students (29.06%) from final year, twenty three (26.74%) from the fourth year, 15 (17.44%) from the third year, 14 (16.27%) from the second year and nine (10.46%) students from the first year participated in the study.

Regarding the sleep patterns, 67 students (77.90%) responded that they don't get enough sleep during their academic year. Thirty five students (40.69%) told they get proper sleep despite their hectic routines.

Certain factors related to the poor quality of sleep were assignments (40.86%), electricity issues (18.28%), irregular ward rotations (16.13%) and hospital duties (12.90%) and commute (11.83%) in case of day scholars.

Factor	1 st year	2 nd year	3 rd year	4 th year	Final year
Ward	0	0	2	4	9
Hospital	0	0	2	3	7
Assignments	3	9	5	7	6
Commute	2	2	3	5	1
Electricity	4	3	3	4	2
Total	9	14	15	23	25

DISCUSSION:

In our study, 77.90% of the students responded that they don't get enough sleep during their academic routines. Out of them, 40.86% of students related this with their routine assignments and examinations. In a review by Curcio et al. it was suggested that the quality and quantity of sleep are closely related to academic performance and learning in students⁷. Other major reasons of sleep disturbances were electricity issues (18.28%), irregular ward rotations (16.13%) and hospital duties (12.90%) and commute (11.83%).

A regular sleep improves the cognitive competencies of students and helps in their memory consolidation as well as getting strong nerves enabling them to handle tough situations. In a study at King Saud University Saudi Arabia, it was seen that those students who performed excellently during their examinations reported that they sleep earlier in the night and have higher sleep duration throughout the week. This study also suggested that students who have decreased sleep in the night, who sleep late and who sleep during the daytime performed average in the examinations. Similar kind of study was also conducted on Brazilian students as well. This study also suggested similar findings i.e. students with proper sleep patterns performed well in their examinations and daily routines [8,9].

There are some limitations to this study i.e. we included a smaller number of students and secondly who didn't compare their academic performance with their sleep patterns. A study including these factors should be conducted.

CONCLUSION:

Most of the medical students have irregular sleep patterns and they don't sleep well. It is associated with their academic assignments, examinations, irregular hospital routines, electricity issues and tiredness after the commute.

CONTRIBUTION OF AUTHORS:

Maria Batool: Data Collection, writing limitations and conclusion section

Aisha Akbar: Writing the results and discussion section

Hira Javaid: Writing the introduction and Methodology section

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